

EFFECTS OF ENVIRONMENTAL ENRICHMENT ON PHYSIOLOGICAL HEALTH AND STRESS BIOMARKERS IN JAPANESE QUAIL (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*)Priyanka Rani ^{1*}, D.K Singh ², Gulab Chandra ³, R.P Diwakar ⁴, Ajit Kumar ⁵, Amit Kumar ⁶, Pratibha Singh ⁷, Pratyush Kumar ⁸, Ganesh ⁹.¹Research Scholar Department of Livestock Production Management SVPUA&T Meerut U.P.²Professor and Head, Department of Livestock Production Management SVPUA&T Meerut U.P.³Assistant Professor Department of Veterinary Physiology and Biochemistry SVPUA&T Meerut U.P.⁴Assistant Professor Department of Veterinary Microbiology, College of Veterinary Science and A.H, ANDUAT, Kumarganj, Ayodhya U.P⁵Assistant Professor Department of Animal Nutrition SVPUA&T Meerut U.P.⁶Professor, Department of Livestock Production Management SVPUA&T Meerut U.P.⁷Research Scholar Department of Veterinary Physiology and Biochemistry SVPUA&T Meerut U.P.⁸Assistant Professor Department of Veterinary Gynaecology and Obstetrics COVAS, Kishanganj, Patna, Bihar.⁹Research Scholar Department of Animal Nutrition College of Veterinary Science and A.H, ANDUAT, Kumarganj, Ayodhya U.P. India.

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Abstract

Japanese quail (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*) are frequently reared in barren housing systems that lack structural complexity, conditions which can elevate stress, promote harmful social interactions, increase injury and mortality, and ultimately reduce productivity. While environmental enrichment is recognized for improving welfare in various poultry species, limited information is available regarding effective enrichment strategies for quail. The present study evaluated the impact of different enrichment types on the welfare and productivity of Japanese quail from 5 to 24 weeks of age. A total of 160 birds were allotted to four treatment groups in a completely randomized design: a control group (no enrichment), T1 (sand bath), T2 (wooden perches), and T3 (sand bath + perches). Data were collected on production performance, immune response (total immunoglobulins and IgG), liver health indicators (AST, ALT, ALP), protein metabolites (total plasma protein, albumin, globulin, cholesterol) and physiological stress markers (heterophils, lymphocytes, H/L ratio, cortisol). Statistical analysis was conducted using one-way ANOVA in SPSS 22.0. The results revealed that the benefits of enrichment were dependent on the type provided, with sand bath enrichment either alone or in combination with perches producing the most favourable outcomes. Enriched groups showed improved welfare parameters and reduced stress-related responses compared to the control. Overall, sand baths emerged as a particularly effective enrichment tool for enhancing welfare and supporting productivity, highlighting their potential for promoting economic sustainability in commercial quail production.

Introduction

Poultry farming is one of the most significant livestock-based occupations in India, offering rapid economic returns and contributing substantially to the livelihood of weaker sections of society. Over recent decades, the sector has expanded from a traditional backyard activity into a highly organized commercial industry. Among poultry species, quails are gaining increasing importance worldwide. Nearly 20 wild and 70 domestic strains of quail have been identified globally (Chang et al., 2005), and quail production serves as a valuable supplement to chicken and duck farming for meeting rising consumer demand for poultry products. Quail eggs account for approximately 10% of the global table egg market, ranking next to chicken eggs (Lukanov, 2019). In India, quails constitute around 0.91% of the national poultry population, and the poultry sector contributes 0.57% to the national GDP and nearly 16% to the livestock GDP. As per the Basic Animal Husbandry Statistics (2019), the country's total poultry population has reached 851.81 million, marking a 16.80% increase from the previous census.

Quails possess several biological and economic advantages that make them ideal for small-scale and backyard farming systems. Their small body size, minimal space requirements, low feed intake, and simple housing needs render them more economical to rear compared to other poultry species. They grow rapidly, reaching maturity within 6 – 7 weeks, and their meat and eggs are nutritionally rich and palatable. Compared with chickens, quails have a higher body weight relative to size, leaner meat, high survival rates, and greater resistance to diseases. Their efficient feed conversion, fast metabolism, and prolific egg-laying capacity further enhance their production efficiency. Additionally, their small size, resilience, and rapid reproductive cycle make them valuable experimental models in studies on nutrition, reproduction, endocrinology, immune function, ageing, and behaviour (Huss et al., 2008; Tserveni-Goussi & Fortomaris, 2011). Their usefulness has been demonstrated in research on feed evaluation (Sigolo et al., 2019; Reda et al., 2020), endocrine mechanisms (Ottinger et al., 2001), immune and ageing physiology (Holmes & Ottinger, 2003), and behavioural analysis (Pittet et al., 2019).

Environmental enrichment (EE) is a management practice that involves improving the physical and social environment of birds to stimulate natural behaviours and enhance welfare (Newberry, 1995). The primary goal of EE is to reduce stress and promote both physical and psychological well-being (Laurence et al., 2015). Welfare, as defined by Broom et al. (1986), reflects an animal's ability to cope with its environment, and the Five Freedoms formulated by the Brambell Committee continue to serve as fundamental principles for evaluating farm animal well-being. Various enrichment strategies such as perches, nest boxes (Guesdon et al., 2006), enriched flooring or litter materials (Blokhuis et al., 1989), and toys or objects like brushes, balls, containers, and plastic tubes (Bari et al., 2020) can enhance the welfare of laying birds. Specially designed toys have also been shown to reduce aggressive behaviours (Gvoryahu et al., 1994), while appropriate stocking density and outdoor access further improve welfare (Campbell et al., 2017).

Environmental enrichment provides birds with greater control over their surroundings (Weinberg & Levine, 1980), enhances adaptability, and reduces stress (Cheng et al., 2002). Research on Japanese quails demonstrates that EE can improve growth performance, immune function, blood biochemical parameters, egg quality, and overall welfare. In light of these findings, the present study was designed to evaluate the effects of environmental enrichment on Physiological Health and Stress Biomarkers in Japanese Quail (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*).

Material and Methods

Entire length of the experiment was 19 weeks. In this experiment five-week-old 160 female grower Japanese quail were purchased and reared for subsequent enrichment trial. The four groups, which comprised of four replicates and 10 quails in each. Groups were named as Control, T₁, T₂ and T₃. T₁ group (sand enriched) birds in this group were provided with plastic circular tubs featuring an open surface area of 2826 cm² and a depth of 16 cm. The tubs were filled with premium play sand (sharp sand) to a depth of 12 cm. To ensure an adequate amount of sand for dust bathing, the sand was replenished daily, T₂ group (wooden perch enriched), this group was supplied with mobile, inverted "U"-shaped wooden perches. Each perch had a ground

clearance of 30 cm and measured 80 cm in length. Wooden sticks with dimensions of 80 × 2 × 2 cm (length × width × height) were used for the construction, T₃ group (combination of sand dust and wooden perch), birds in this group had access to both sand dust and wooden perches for enrichment and control group.

The experiment commenced after a seven-day acclimatization period during which the birds were allowed to adapt to their new environment. All the Japanese quail birds were reared under similar managerial and hygienic conditions in a deep litter system of rearing with well-ventilated pens. The floor was thoroughly cleaned, disinfected, and dried before spreading the dry rice husk as bedding material. The rice husk was evenly spread in 6-8 cm thickness. Florescent tube lights (38 watts each) were fitted at appropriate heights to provide uniform lighting. A photo-scheduled program (16 hours light and 8 hours dark) was used throughout the experiment.

The Japanese quails in the various treatment groups were given free access to fresh and clean water. Basal diets were offered ad libitum, twice daily. Japanese quails were fed on a basal commercial diet from the start of the experiment until the end based on the requirements of Japanese quails outlined in NRC (1994).

Representative samples of basal diet were analyzed for their nutrient composition viz. moisture, dry matter, crude protein, total ash, and ether extract as per AOAC (2005). Immune response and blood biochemical parameters Blood samples were collected randomly from 12 birds per treatment on the 6th and 24th week of the experiment. Blood 3 ml was collected from the Jugular vein with the help of a sterile syringe and poured into an anticoagulant EDTA-coated vial. Blood samples were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes for plasma separation. The supernatant was decanted into a duplicate 1.5 ml Eppendorf tube and stored at (-20 °C) until analyze Enzyme estimation was done within 24 hours of collection.

To determine total protein, 10 µL of each plasma sample was transferred into 10×75 mm test tubes in duplicate, followed by the addition of 1000 µL of working biuret reagent. For the blank, 10 µL of distilled water was used, and for the standard, 10 µL of protein standard solution (6.5 g/dL) was taken; both were treated similarly with 1000 µL of working biuret reagent. All tubes were mixed thoroughly and allowed to stand at room temperature for one minute. The spectrophotometer was set to zero using the reagent blank, and absorbance values for both the standard and test samples were recorded at 578 nm. Total protein concentration for each sample was then calculated using the standard formula and expressed as g/dL.

Plasma albumin concentration was determined using a commercial BCG-based kit (ERBA Diagnostics, Mannheim, Germany). In this method, albumin binds with Bromocresol Green in a buffered medium to form a green complex, the intensity of which is measured at 630 nm using a UV-Spectrophotometer. For analysis, 10 µL of plasma, distilled water (blank), or albumin standard (4 g/dL) was mixed with 1000 µL of working reagent in duplicate and incubated for one minute at room temperature. Absorbance was recorded at 630 nm after blank calibration, and albumin concentration was calculated using the standard curve and expressed in g/dL.

Plasma total cholesterol was estimated using a commercial enzymatic kit (ERBA Diagnostics, Mannheim, Germany). Esterified cholesterol was hydrolysed and oxidized to generate hydrogen peroxide, which reacted with phenol and 4-aminoantipyrine in the presence of peroxidase to form a red quinoneimine dye. The colour intensity, proportional to cholesterol concentration, was measured at 505 nm. For the assay, 10 µL of plasma, reagent blank, and standard (200 mg/dL) were each mixed with 1000 µL of working reagent and incubated for 10 minutes at room temperature. Absorbance was recorded at 505 nm after blank calibration, and cholesterol concentration was calculated using the standard formula and expressed in mg/dL.

Plasma SGPT (ALT) activity was analyzed using a commercial diagnostic kit (ERBA Diagnostics, Mannheim, Germany). The assay is based on ALT-mediated transamination of L-alanine and α-ketoglutarate to form pyruvate, which reacts with 2,4-

dinitrophenylhydrazine in alkaline medium to produce a brown hydrazone complex measurable spectrophotometrically. Absorbance was recorded at 340 nm using a UV-Spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific™, USA), and enzyme activity was expressed in U/L. For estimation, 100 µL of plasma was incubated with 1000 µL of working ALT reagent in duplicate, with purified water serving as the blank. Absorbance was recorded after 60 seconds and then every 30 seconds up to 120 seconds, and the average change in absorbance per minute was used to calculate SGPT activity.

Alkaline phosphatase Plasma alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity was determined using a commercial diagnostic kit provided by ERBA Diagnostics, Mannheim, Germany. The assay is based on the enzymatic hydrolysis of p-nitrophenyl phosphate (pNPP) at pH 10.3, producing yellow-coloured p-nitrophenol and phosphate. The rate of colour development, measured kinetically at 405 nm using a UV-Spectrophotometer, is directly proportional to ALP activity in the sample. Results were calculated according to the manufacturer's protocol and expressed as units per liter.

Total plasma immunoglobulins were estimated using the zinc turbidity method (McEwan and Fisher, 1970). Plasma (100 µL) was mixed with 12 mL of zinc sulfate reagent and held at room temperature for 1 hour. Rabbit gamma globulin standards (12–50 mg/mL), prepared in fetal calf serum, were processed similarly. Optical density was measured at 460 nm, and immunoglobulin concentration was determined from the standard curve and expressed as mg/mL. Plasma IgG concentration was determined using a commercial ELISA kit based on a sandwich enzyme immunoassay. Standards and samples were added to antibody-coated wells, followed by biotin-conjugated detection antibody, streptavidin–HRP and TMB substrate to generate a colour reaction proportional to IgG content. After stopping the reaction with sulphuric acid, absorbance was measured at 450 nm. IgG values were calculated from the corresponding standard curve.

For estimating the H:L ratio in the blood, the blood smears were prepared on clean glass slides on the 6th and 24th week of the experiment. The smears were allowed to dry and then fixed with methanol before staining. After the fixation of the smears, the slides were stained by the standard method of Giemsa staining. After staining, slides were allowed to dry and examined under the microscope at 100X power with oil immersion. 100 cells, i.e., heterophils and/or lymphocytes counted in each smear. The ratio was further calculated by the following formula as per Wall et al. (2008).

Plasma cortisol concentration was determined using a commercial ELISA kit supplied by Cal Biotech. All reagents were brought to room temperature and mixed gently prior to use. The required number of coated microplate strips was placed into the holder, and 25 µL of cortisol standards and plasma samples were pipetted into respective wells. Subsequently, 50 µL of biotin reagent and 100 µL of cortisol enzyme conjugate were added to each well, mixed, and incubated for 60 minutes at room temperature (20–25 °C). After incubation, the wells were washed three times with wash buffer and blotted dry. Then, 100 µL of TMB substrate was added and incubated for 15 minutes at room temperature. The reaction was stopped by adding 50 µL stop solution, and absorbance was measured at 450 nm within 20 minutes. Cortisol concentrations were calculated by comparing sample absorbance values to the standard curve.

Results

The humoral immune response of the experimental birds indicated that TIg and IgG levels did not differ significantly at the 6th week; however, a marked increase ($P < 0.05$) was observed at the 24th week, wherein T₁ and T₃ groups recorded significantly higher and comparable TIg (51.897 and 51.59 mg/dl) and IgG (39.70 and 39.62 mg/dl) concentrations, respectively, than the control and T₂ groups, demonstrating an immunoenhancing effect of these treatments during later growth. Mean AST values differed significantly at both intervals ($P < 0.05$), with the T₂ group showing lower activity at the 6th week and the T₁ group exhibiting the lowest values at the 24th week. In contrast, ALT activity remained statistically similar across all treatments, while

ALP values were comparable at the 6th week but significantly higher ($P<0.05$) in all treated groups than in the control at the 24th week. Total protein concentration differed significantly ($P<0.05$), with the T₁ group consistently showing the highest values at both sampling stages. Albumin values were statistically comparable overall; however, the T₁ group recorded a significantly higher level at the 6th week. Globulin concentration followed a similar trend, showing significantly higher values in T₁ at the 24th week. Plasma cholesterol levels remained unaffected by dietary treatments throughout the experimental period. Hematological indicators reflected a reduction in physiological stress

in treated groups, as heterophil counts were significantly lower ($P<0.05$), while lymphocyte percentages were significantly higher in T₁ and T₃ at the 24th week. Consequently, the H/L ratio and serum cortisol concentration showed a significant reduction in these two groups at the later sampling point, indicating improved stress tolerance. Collectively, the results suggest that dietary supplementation in T₁ and T₃ improved immune competence, protein metabolism, and stress resilience, particularly at the advanced stage of growth.

Table No.1 . Shows effects of Environmental Enrichment on Physiological Health and Stress Biomarkers in Japanese Quail.

Variables	Week	Group				SEM	P Value
		Control	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃		
TIg	Mean	40.18 ^a	43.50 ^b	39.68 ^a	43.69 ^b	0.40	< 0.001
IgG	Mean	30.30 ^a	32.87 ^b	29.44 ^a	33.16 ^b	0.39	< 0.001
AST (IU/L)	Mean	257.91 ^b	253.67 ^a	257.30 ^{ab}	255.79 ^{ab}	0.93	0.040
ALT (IU/L)	Mean	9.88	11.92	10.04	11.35	0.66	0.063
ALP (IU/L)	Mean	97.62	99.40	95.55	98.18	1.15	0.101
Total Protein	Mean	4.30 ^a	4.43 ^b	4.29 ^a	4.34 ^a	0.02	0.001
Albumin (g/dl)	Mean	1.59	1.66	1.62	1.61	0.02	0.064
Globulin (g/dl)	Mean	2.71 ^{ab}	2.77 ^b	2.70 ^a	2.73 ^{ab}	0.03	0.021
Cholesterol (mg/dl)	Mean	172.43	176.42	173.31	178.17	5.54	0.781
Heterophil	Mean	36.13 ^c	30.38 ^a	33.25 ^b	30.63 ^a	0.67	0.001
Lymphocyte	Mean	55.38 ^a	61.63 ^c	58.00 ^b	63.00 ^c	0.80	0.001
H/L	Mean	0.65 ^c	0.51 ^a	0.57 ^b	0.50 ^a	0.01	0.001
Cortisol (ng/ml)	Mean	175.54 ^b	105.26 ^a	177.05 ^b	106.62 ^a	1.11	0.001

T₁ (sand bath); T₂ (perch); T₃(sand bath + perch)

^{abc}Means bearing different superscripts in a row differ significantly at ($P<0.05$)

Discussion

The present study revealed that environmental enrichment had a marked influence on immunological, physiological, and biochemical parameters of Japanese quail. Significant increases in total immunoglobulin (TIg) and IgG concentrations in T₁ and T₃ groups at the 24th week indicate improved humoral immunity over time. Enrichment elements such as sand baths and perches appeared to enhance immune responsiveness, likely by reducing stress and promoting natural behaviors. These findings are supported by Bizeray et al. (2002), who reported that enriched environments improved welfare and reduced physiological stress, consequently enhancing immune function. Similar reports suggest that environmental enrichment enhances immune system activity in poultry by promoting behavioral engagement and lowering chronic stress.

Liver function indicators provided insight into the physiological impact of enrichment. A significant decrease in AST concentrations was observed, with the T₁ group consistently showing the lowest values at both sampling points. This reduction may reflect lower tissue

damage or improved metabolic balance resulting from reduced stress. Although ALT values remained statistically unchanged, the findings are partially consistent with those of Hassan et al. (2013), who noted that improvements in welfare due to enrichment did not always translate to immediate changes in liver enzymes. Likewise, Moe et al. (2010) and El-Deen et al. (2008) reported non-significant differences in AST and ALT in enriched quail, suggesting that liver enzymes may require prolonged physiological change to show measurable effects. ALP levels were higher in treated groups, with the control group showing significantly lower values at 24 weeks. This may indicate better bone metabolism and metabolic activity in enriched birds. El-Full (2001) also reported slight improvements in ALP in enriched quail, although Bizeray et al. (2002) noted that ALP responses can vary based on age, nutrition, and health rather than enrichment alone.

Total plasma protein was significantly higher in the T₁ group, suggesting improved protein metabolism and systemic health. Earlier studies demonstrate that enrichment increases physical activity and reduces stress, which may enhance nutrient utilization and protein

synthesis (Gitoee et al., 2018; Moe et al., 2010; Yildirim & Taskin, 2017). Consistent growth patterns in enriched quail observed by Son et al. (2022) further support the present findings. Albumin values showed a significant increase at the sixth week in T₁ quail, indicating an early metabolic response to enrichment, though long-term differences were not maintained. Similar outcomes were reported by Bizeray et al. (2002) and Meluzzi et al. (1992), who found no uniform influence of enrichment on plasma albumin levels. In contrast, globulin values were consistently higher in T₁ groups at both sampling periods, demonstrating improved immune protein production. These results align with El-Shafei et al. (2012), Hassan et al. (2013), and Moe et al. (2010), who emphasized the role of enriched housing in improving immunological health and plasma globulin levels.

Environmental enrichment did not significantly influence plasma cholesterol, consistent with Yildirim & Taskin (2017) and Meluzzi et al. (1992), who reported no significant effects of enrichment on cholesterol metabolism. In contrast, hematological parameters associated with stress showed notable improvement. Heterophil counts were significantly lower in T₁ and T₃ groups, while lymphocyte counts were significantly higher, indicating reduced physiological stress and enhanced immunity. These trends reflect findings by Jones et al. (2005) and Tahamtani et al. (2016), who demonstrated that enrichment reduces corticosterone secretion and heterophil frequency. The significantly lower H/L ratio in T₁ and T₃ quail further supports this interpretation. This stress-reducing effect of enrichment has been well documented, with previous studies identifying the H/L ratio as a reliable chronic stress biomarker in poultry (Maxwell, 1993; Campo et al., 2008; Lindqvist et al., 2009).

Cortisol concentrations were also significantly reduced in enriched groups, reaffirming that enrichment mitigates chronic stress. The pronounced decline in cortisol at the 24th week in T₁ and T₃ groups indicates that long-term exposure to behavioral enrichment activities perching, dust bathing, and foraging promotes psychological comfort and reduces neuroendocrine stress responses. Comparable reductions in cortisol due to enrichment have been reported by Campo et al. (2008), Lindqvist et al. (2009), Miller & Mench (2005), Meehan et al. (2003), and Ramankevich et al. (2022).

Overall, the study demonstrates that environmental enrichment, particularly through sand baths and perches, improves immune function, reduces stress, and enhances metabolic stability in Japanese quail. These findings emphasize the importance of providing naturalistic environments in commercial production systems to promote welfare, physiological resilience, and overall health.

Conclusion

The present study demonstrates that environmental enrichment exerts a beneficial influence on the physiological, immunological, and biochemical status of Japanese quail. Enrichment strategies incorporating sand baths and perches significantly enhanced humoral immunity, improved protein metabolism, and reduced physiological stress, as evidenced by higher TIg, IgG, and globulin levels, along with lower heterophil counts, H/L ratios, and cortisol concentrations. Although some biochemical parameters such as ALT and cholesterol remained unaffected, notable improvements in AST, ALP, and total plasma protein indicate enhanced metabolic stability and overall health. The consistent reduction in stress biomarkers highlights the importance of enrichment in promoting welfare and resilience in quail. Overall, the findings underscore that providing simple, naturalistic enrichments can markedly improve health and welfare outcomes in Japanese quail. Integrating such enrichment elements into commercial production systems can support better immune competence, reduced stress, and improved physiological performance, thereby contributing to more sustainable and welfare-oriented poultry management practices.

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